

Propensity score weighted Bayesian additive regression tree (BART) for incorporating external data

Sanwayee Kundu and Elizabeth H. Slate

Department of Statistics, Florida State University, Tallahassee

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Abstract

Clinical trials are essential for evaluating new medical treatments, and previous literature shows that supplementing the control arm with external data increases efficiency by enhancing statistical power and reducing the need for extensive control group recruitment. However, a hybrid control arm, while serving as a substitute for a traditional control arm, requires statistical adjustments to ensure accurate estimation of treatment effects. In this paper, we propose integrating propensity scores with Bayesian Additive Regression Trees (BART) to facilitate statistically adjusted borrowing of external data for better treatment effect estimation. The flexibility of BART, combined with the covariate balancing power of propensity scores, has potential to enable researchers to effectively incorporate external data into trials, improving the accuracy of treatment estimates while controlling for potential confounding. We employ propensity scores with BART in three distinct approaches, and simulations show that these combined methods perform comparably, if not superiorly, to standard BART. The methods are illustrated using real-life breast cancer datasets.

1 Introduction

Testing new medical treatments through clinical trials plays a vital role in advancing healthcare, and improving the efficiency of these trials is essential for accelerating the development and approval of innovative therapies that can enhance patient outcomes. In the pursuit of expediting clinical trials, borrowing external control data emerges as a strategic approach (Pocock, 1976), facilitating a more efficient evaluation of new medical interventions while respecting ethical considerations (Schmidli et al., 2019) (Chen et al., 2021). This paper introduces combining Bayesian Additive Regression Trees (BART) with propensity score weights for the incorporation of covariate information from external data to estimate treatment effects in current clinical trials. The flexibility of BART along with covariate balancing property of propensity scores empowers researchers to robustly integrate external data into clinical trials, facilitating an understanding of treatment effects while addressing potential confounding factors. The study aims to evaluate how propensity scores incorporated with BART influences trial accuracy and robustness, potentially speeding up the discovery of effective treatments.

2 Background

The use of external control data has been on the rise due to the abundance of clinical study data collected from randomized controlled trials (RCTs), medical registries, etc. and the time-consuming, costly and ethically demanding nature of RCTs. The control arm of an ongoing RCT can be supplemented using the external control data to reduce burden on both patients and trial conductors. Hence, borrowing from external sources seems attractive as it can potentially decrease the mean squared error of the estimated treatment effects and increase the power of identifying effective treatment. However, this also introduces challenges such as confounding and selection bias. BART can

learn covariate-response relationships to overcome these challenges as it is a data-driven algorithm that automatically adjusts for patient-level covariates and captures heterogeneity among the different data sources. Consequently, using BART when borrowing external control data may help improve precision and validity of causal inference.

The incorporation of propensity scores into this framework may further fortifies the robustness of estimating treatment effects. Propensity scores serve as a valuable tool to address confounding and enhance the comparability of control groups from different sources. Originally, the propensity score, introduced by [Rosenbaum and Rubin \(1983\)](#), was defined as the conditional probability of being assigned to the treatment group, given a set of observed covariates. In the external data borrowing context, however, it is defined as the conditional probability of belonging to the current study given the covariates. This propensity score accounts for the similarity between the subjects, with respect to observed covariates in the control groups of the current and external trials. By including propensity scores alongside BART, the model may gain additional strength in accounting for potential biases introduced by differences in observed covariates. This dual approach, leveraging both BART's adaptability and propensity scores' ability to balance covariates, contributes to a more resilient and accurate estimation of treatment effects when augmenting the control arm with external data. The combination of these methodologies fosters a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of causal relationships, improving the overall precision and validity of the inference process.

Adjusting for potential and observed confounders in external data borrowing has been addressed using propensity score methods, aiming to make external and current subjects similar with respect to baseline covariates. However, the reliance on the critical assumption that all relevant confounders have been considered makes propensity score methods susceptible to differences arising from unmeasured confounding. On the other hand, Bayesian borrowing methods, like power priors ([Chen and Ibrahim, 2000](#)) ([Berry et al., 2010](#)), explicitly down-weight the whole external data without considering subject-wise covariate similarity. Further research into this topic has led to combining the propensity score and Bayesian borrowing methods to overcome their respective drawbacks.

In the context of external data borrowing, prevailing methodologies in the literature often impose restrictive parametric assumptions. BART has emerged as an alternative approach, leveraging its data-driven nature and the ability to adaptively capture patient-level covariate information, thereby enhancing the precision of estimates by amalgamating information from diverse data sources. While estimating the causal effect of treatment is fundamental in both RCTs and external data borrowing, traditional RCTs inherently establish causality through randomized treatment assignment and balanced measured confounders in both arms. However, borrowing data from external trials lacks randomization, as the borrowed data does not undergo the randomization process. Consequently, the pooling of randomized subjects from the current trial with borrowed subjects does not guarantee causality in treatment effect estimation. To address this and contend with the variability in patient characteristics between current and external studies, BART has been proposed to model the intricate relationship among patient outcomes, covariates, and an indicator denoting the data source ([Zhou and Ji, 2021](#)).

To guard against potential source bias, [Carnegie et al. \(2019\)](#) suggest including an estimate of propensity score as a covariate when using BART for causal inference. In finite samples, [Hahn et al. \(2017\)](#) find this approach to reduce the bias of regularized treatment effect estimates. Hence, they recommend including an estimate of propensity score as a covariate regardless of the algorithms or models used to estimate treatment effect since regularization is necessary to estimate heterogeneous effects non- or semi-parametrically or in high dimension. Our proposed method is to apply a propensity score weighted BART model to external data borrowing for estimation of causal treatment effects.

3 Methodology

3.1 Propensity scores

Adjusting for potential and observed confounders is a challenge in external data borrowing that has been dealt with in recent years using propensity score methods. When borrowing data from external

trials, subjects in external control and current study are not randomized, as in randomized controlled trials (RCTs). RCTs, being the gold standard in measuring efficacy of drugs, are efficient due to randomization of subjects in the control and treatment arm. This randomization balances confounders in each arm and hence, no adjustments to the results are required. In propensity score methods and external data borrowing, in general, our aim is to make the external and current subjects similar with respect to their baseline covariates, to ensure comparability of the responses from external and current subjects in the control arm. Bayesian methods prove superior as they can seamlessly integrate external data in the form of prior distributions and provide flexible frameworks which allow partial borrowing based on the similarity between external and current data (Chen and Ibrahim, 2000) (Hobbs et al., 2012). However, they lack transparency in clearly identifying which patients’ data are used and in what volume, unlike propensity score methods—such as stratification, matching, inverse probability weighting, and covariate adjustment—which explicitly define how data from individual patients contribute to the analysis. Nonetheless, propensity score methods often fail to account for differences due to unmeasured confounders, making them unreliable when disparities between external and current data arise from unmeasured confounding. While Bayesian methods can learn latent patterns, they do not directly solve unmeasured confounding unless unmeasured confounders are reflected through the observed data.

Subsequent research has led to combining the propensity score and Bayesian methods to overcome their respective drawbacks. Wang et al. (2021) propose augmenting the control arm of a 2:1 randomized clinical trial with external data using propensity score methods to pre-select relevant subjects while making use of Bayesian commensurate priors to effectively leverage the real-world external data. They conclude through extensive simulations that in various simulation settings, PS matching and weighting paired with commensurate priors produce acceptable statistical properties. In single arm study settings, Wang et al. (2019) suggest stratification by the PS and specifying a power prior within each stratum. Simulations are carried out with and without stratification which support superiority of stratification with respect to bias and MSEs. Lin et al. (2018) focus on constructing an informative prior using propensity score matching for augmentation of the control arm with external data. They apply generalized boosted models, a non-parametric and data adaptive technique to estimate the propensity scores, which is otherwise accomplished with a parametric logistic regression model using all the covariates that are linear and additive on the log-odds scale. Although most of the research addresses augmentation of the control arm of the active study with external data, Li et al. (2021) propose augmentation of both arms of an RCT. Using Bayesian (propensity score-integrated power prior) as well as frequentist (propensity score-integrated composite likelihood) approaches, they describe appropriate statistical procedures for study and analysis.

In case of observational studies, propensity score is defined as the conditional probability of being assigned to a particular treatment given observed covariates. However, in the context of external control data borrowing, the propensity score $e(X)$ is the conditional probability of membership of a subject in the current study, given the baseline covariates (denoted by \mathbf{X}).

$$e(X) = P[S = 0|X],$$

where, $S = 0$ indicates subjects from the current study and $S = s$ for subjects in the s^{th} external study.

3.1.1 Inverse probability weighting

By weighting patients, this technique creates a pseudo-population made up of the weighted subjects in the current and external trials, ensuring that the covariate distributions of the propensity score (PS) adjusted populations are similar. Similar to inverse probability treatment weight, this weighting allows subjects with underrepresented traits to contribute more in the analysis by giving external subjects a weight of $1/PS$ and current subjects a weight of $1/(1 - PS)$. These scores are interpreted as the probability of an individual from the current trial (Wang et al., 2021). The weights are usually stabilized to alleviate extreme values of propensity scores.

3.2 BART

For external data borrowing, methods that have been defined in literature make stringent parametric assumptions. BART has been developed as an alternative, as it is data-driven, and since it captures patient level covariate information, it can adaptively pool information from data sources to produce more accurate estimates. Similar to RCTs, it is important to estimate the causal effect of treatment when borrowing data from external sources. The treatment effects estimated in traditional RCTs are causal by design. The measured confounders are balanced in both arms of the RCTs, which provides for causality, but when borrowing data from external trials, the borrowed data does not get randomized. Hence, we have randomized subjects in the current trial pooled with borrowed subjects, which does not ensure causality when estimating treatment effects. In order to tackle this and the issue of patient characteristics being different for the current and external studies, BART has been proposed to model the relationship between patient outcome, covariates and an indicator of data source (Zhou and Ji, 2021).

3.2.1 Estimating treatment effects

Zhou and Ji (2021) define S_i be an indicator for data source, i.e., $S_i = 0$ for current study and $S_i = s$, where $s \in \{1, 2, \dots, J\}$ for s^{th} external study, for subject i . Let $T_i = 1$ (or 0) denoted the treatment assignment of subject i and it is also assumed that external study individuals receive control whereas, current study subjects are randomized to both treatment and control arm. The potential outcomes are denoted by $Y_i(1)$ or $Y_i(0)$ which cannot be observed simultaneously, hence observed outcome is defined as $Y_i = Y_i(1)T_i + Y_i(0)(1 - T_i)$. Zhou and Ji (2021), however, focus on treatment effect $Y_i(1) - Y_i(0)$, the difference between potential outcomes along with patient-level covariates $\mathbf{X}_i = (X_{i1}, \dots, X_{iQ})$ for Q patients in both current and external study.

The conditional average treatment effect (CATE) and population average treatment effect (PATE) are defined, as estimation of average treatment effect (ATE) is the main goal in clinical studies

$$\Delta_C = \frac{1}{N_{trial}} \sum_{i:S_i=0} E[Y_i(1) - Y_i(0)|\mathbf{X}_i, S_i = 0], \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta_P = E[Y_i(1) - Y_i(0)|S_i = 0] = E[E[Y_i(1) - Y_i(0)|\mathbf{X}_i, S_i = 0]] \quad (2)$$

respectively.

The distribution of $[Y(t)|\mathbf{X}, S]$ is the response surface which is the potential outcome for assigned treatment group conditional on the covariates and source. Under the unconfoundedness condition that potential outcome is independent of the treatment group assignment given covariates and source or $[Y(0), Y(1) \perp T|\mathbf{X}, S = 0]$ (satisfied for RCTs), we have

$$E[Y(t)|\mathbf{X}, S = 0] = E[Y(t)|T = t, \mathbf{X}, S = 0] = E[Y|T = t, \mathbf{X}, S = 0].$$

Hence,

$$E[Y(1) - Y(0)|\mathbf{X}, S = 0] = E[Y|T = 1, \mathbf{X}, S = 0] - E[Y|T = 0, \mathbf{X}, S = 0] \triangleq \delta(\mathbf{X})$$

and

$$\Delta_C = \frac{1}{N_{trial}} \sum_{i:S_i=0} \delta(\mathbf{X}_i) \quad \Delta_P = \int \delta(\mathbf{x})p(\mathbf{x}|S = 0)d\mathbf{x}, \quad (3)$$

where $p(\mathbf{x}|S = 0)$ is the distribution of patient characteristics over trial population. $\delta(\mathbf{x})$ is defined as the conditional treatment effect (Zhou and Ji, 2021).

Zhou and Ji (2021) also explain that incorporation of external data could improve the estimation of $E[Y|T = 0, \mathbf{X}, S = 0]$ and ideally the control outcome Y and data source S are conditionally independent of given the covariate \mathbf{X} , i.e., $[Y \perp S|T = 0, \mathbf{X}]$. Hence, $[Y|T = 0, \mathbf{X}, S = s] \stackrel{d}{=} [Y|T = 0, \mathbf{X}]$ where $\stackrel{d}{=}$ denotes equality in distribution. The current and external control data can

be pooled together to estimate $E[Y|T = 0, \mathbf{X}]$, under the assumption of conditional independence. However, this assumption may not hold in reality due to unmeasured confounding covariates. The objective for [Zhou and Ji \(2021\)](#) is to capture the discrepancy in $[Y|T = 0, \mathbf{X}]$ across data sources by modeling the relationship among Y , \mathbf{X} and S for the control data.

3.2.2 BART for data borrowing

[Zhou and Ji \(2021\)](#) specify the probability model separately for control and treatment groups,

$$\begin{aligned} [Y|T = 0, \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}, S = s] &= f_0(\mathbf{x}, s) + \epsilon_0, \quad \text{and} \\ [Y|T = 1, \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}, S = 0] &= f_1(\mathbf{x}) + \epsilon_1, \end{aligned}$$

where $\epsilon_0 \sim N(0, \sigma_0^2)$ and $\epsilon_1 \sim N(0, \sigma_1^2)$. Therefore,

$$\delta(\mathbf{x}) = f_1(\mathbf{x}) - f_0(\mathbf{x}, 0).$$

And the BART model for f_0 and f_1 are specified as,

$$f_0(\mathbf{x}, s) = \sum_{j=1}^{m_0} g(\mathbf{x}, s; \mathcal{T}_{0j}, \mu_{0j}) \quad \text{and} \quad f_1(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{j=1}^{m_1} g(\mathbf{x}; \mathcal{T}_{1j}, \mu_{1j}).$$

All properties of BART describe in section 2.2, carries over to BART for data borrowing with data source as an added covariate. A Markov chain Monte Carlo algorithm is employed to implement posterior inference for a BART model. In particular, the algorithm generates K draws from the joint posterior distribution of the model parameters ([Zhou and Ji, 2021](#)),

$$\begin{aligned} \{(\mathcal{T}_{01}^{(k)}, \mu_{01}^{(k)}), \dots, (\mathcal{T}_{0m_0}^{(k)}, \mu_{0m_0}^{(k)}), \sigma_0^{(k)} | l = 1, 2, \dots, K\} \quad \text{and} \\ \{(\mathcal{T}_{11}^{(k)}, \mu_{11}^{(k)}), \dots, (\mathcal{T}_{1m_1}^{(k)}, \mu_{1m_1}^{(k)}), \sigma_1^{(k)} | l = 1, 2, \dots, K\}. \end{aligned}$$

For a specific patient in the current trial ($s=0$) with covariate values \mathbf{x}^* , the posterior samples of $f_0(\mathbf{x}^*, 0)$ and $f_1(\mathbf{x}^*)$ can be calculated by

$$f_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{x}^*, 0) = \sum_{j=1}^{m_0} g(\mathbf{x}^*, s; \mathcal{T}_{0j}^{(k)}, \mu_{0j}^{(k)}) \quad \text{and} \quad f_1^{(k)}(\mathbf{x}^*) = \sum_{j=1}^{m_1} g(\mathbf{x}^*; \mathcal{T}_{1j}^{(k)}, \mu_{1j}^{(k)}), \quad \text{respectively.}$$

The posterior samples of the conditional treatment effect at \mathbf{x}^* , $\delta(\mathbf{x}^*)$, are given by $\delta^{(k)}(\mathbf{x}^*) = f_1^{(k)}(\mathbf{x}^*) - f_0^{(k)}(\mathbf{x}^*, 0)$ for $l = 1, 2, \dots, K$ ([Zhou and Ji, 2021](#)).

3.2.3 BART with propensity score as covariate (psBART)

To guard against potential source bias, [Carnegie et al. \(2019\)](#) suggest including an estimate of propensity score as a covariate when using BART for causal inference. In finite samples, [Hahn et al. \(2017\)](#) find this approach to reduce the bias of regularized treatment effect estimates. Hence, they recommend including an estimate of propensity score as a covariate regardless of the algorithms or models used to estimate treatment effect since regularization is necessary to estimate heterogeneous effects non- or semiparametrically or in high dimension. Our proposed method is to apply propensity score BART model to external data borrowing for estimation of causal treatment effects. [Hahn et al. \(2017\)](#) estimate propensity scores $\pi(x) = P[S = 0|x]$ using BART and includes $\hat{\pi}(x)$ as an extra predictor variable. The updated probability models for control and treatment groups are defined as,

$$\begin{aligned} [Y|T = 0, \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}, S = s] &= f_0(\mathbf{x}, \hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x}), s) + \epsilon_0, \quad \text{and} \\ [Y|T = 1, \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}, S = 0] &= f_1(\mathbf{x}, \hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x})) + \epsilon_1, \end{aligned}$$

where $\epsilon_0 \sim N(0, \sigma_0^2)$ and $\epsilon_1 \sim N(0, \sigma_1^2)$. Therefore,

$$\delta(\mathbf{x}) = f_1(\mathbf{x}, \hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x})) - f_0(\mathbf{x}, \hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x}), 0).$$

And the ps-BART models are specified as,

$$f_0(\mathbf{x}, \hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x}), s) = \sum_{j=1}^{m_0} g(\mathbf{x}, \hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x}), s; \mathcal{T}_{0j}, \mu_{0j}) \quad \text{and} \quad f_1(\mathbf{x}, \hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x})) = \sum_{j=1}^{m_1} g(\mathbf{x}, \hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x}); \mathcal{T}_{1j}, \mu_{1j}).$$

3.2.4 BART with propensity score as weights (ps-wBART)

Similar to the concept of inverse probability treatment weighting, using propensity score as weights can allow subjects with under-represented traits to contribute more in the analysis by giving external source subjects a weight of $1/PS$ and current subjects a weight of $1/(1 - PS)$. Since propensity scores weighting can potentially increase the power and effect size by borrowing from external study, our proposal is to integrate propensity score weighting with BART. After estimating the propensity scores, the observations can be weighted and the model can be specified as,

$$\begin{aligned} [Y|T = 0, \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}, S = s] &= f_0(\mathbf{x}, s) + \epsilon_0, \quad \text{and} \\ [Y|T = 1, \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}, S = 0] &= f_1(\mathbf{x}) + \epsilon_1, \end{aligned}$$

where, $\epsilon_0 \sim N\left(0, \frac{\sigma_0^2}{w}\right)$ and $\epsilon_1 \sim N\left(0, \frac{\sigma_1^2}{w}\right)$, w being the weights i.e., propensity scores.

3.2.5 BART with propensity score as the only covariate (psonlyBART)

As the same suggests, psonlyBART has only the propensity score as the covariate,

$$\begin{aligned} (Y|T = 0, \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}, S = s) &= f_0(\hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x}), s) + \epsilon_0, \quad \text{and} \\ (Y|T = 1, \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}, S = 0) &= f_1(\hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x})) + \epsilon_1, \end{aligned}$$

where $\epsilon_0 \sim N(0, \sigma_0^2)$ and $\epsilon_1 \sim N(0, \sigma_1^2)$. Therefore,

$$\delta(\mathbf{x}) = f_1(\hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x})) - f_0(\hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x}), 0).$$

And the psonlyBART models are specified as,

$$f_0(\hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x}), s) = \sum_{i=1}^{m_0} g(\hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x}), s; \mathcal{T}_{0i}, \mu_{0i}) \quad \text{and} \quad f_1(\hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x})) = \sum_{i=1}^{m_1} g(\hat{\pi}(\mathbf{x}); \mathcal{T}_{1i}, \mu_{1i}).$$

4 Simulations

One of the objectives of this essay is to assess the performance of the aforementioned methods at varying levels heterogeneity of covariate distribution among data sources, hence, we propose three different simulation scenarios. For BART, psBART, psonlyBART we use the bartMachine package (Kapelner and Bleich, 2016) and for ps-wBART we use the BART package (Sparapani et al., 2021) in R. The number of subjects in the current and external trial, which are mutually independent, is 100 and 200 respectively. For 1000 replications of generated data, with 50 trees for each BART fit, we run MCMC simulations for 1100 iterations with the first 100 draws discarded as burn-ins (Zhou and Ji, 2021).

The distribution of the univariate covariate X is held fixed for the current trial, and varies for the external control subjects for the three scenarios. The current trial distribution of X is set as,

$$X|S = 0 \sim N(0.7, 0.2^2).$$

The treatment assignment in the current trial is generated as $T|S = 0 \sim Ber(0.8)$. The outcome is assumed to exhibit a nonlinear relationship with X (Zhou and Ji, 2021),

$$Y|T, X \sim N(1 - 0.16T + T(X - 1)^2 - (1 - T)X^2, 0.1^2).$$

The three scenarios are defined by the degree to which the covariate distribution in the external data overlaps with the current trial data.

Scenario I 100% overlap

$$X|S = 1 \sim N(0.7, 0.2^2).$$

Scenario II 54% overlap

$$X|S = 1 \sim N(0.4, 0.4^2).$$

Scenario III 39% overlap

$$X|S = 1 \sim N(0.2, 0.6^2).$$

Figure 1: Simulation scenarios.

Scenario	Method	CATE	Bias	95% CI	CI Length	RMSE
1	BART	0.501	0.001	0.436, 0.571	0.135	0.034
	psBART	0.500	0.000	0.436, 0.568	0.132	0.036
	ps-wBART	0.498	-0.002	0.431, 0.566	0.135	0.035
	psonlyBART	0.504	0.004	0.389, 0.638	0.249	0.062
2	BART	0.506	0.006	0.436, 0.577	0.141	0.036
	psBART	0.507	0.007	0.438, 0.577	0.139	0.036
	ps-wBART	0.492	-0.008	0.422, 0.560	0.138	0.036
	psonlyBART	0.511	0.011	0.396, 0.634	0.238	0.062
3	BART	0.507	0.007	0.438, 0.579	0.141	0.036
	psBART	0.507	0.007	0.439, 0.578	0.139	0.036
	ps-wBART	0.489	-0.011	0.422, 0.555	0.133	0.036
	psonlyBART	0.515	0.015	0.391, 0.646	0.255	0.068

Table 1: Comparison of CATE estimators across scenarios and methods.

Figure 1 shows the overlap between the covariate distributions of current and external trials mentioned in the three scenarios. Each dataset has the following columns: x , y , s and t . Propensity scores $P[S = 0|X]$ are estimated from all subjects data using BART and the fitted or each subject forms another column. Then, the BART models needed for our methods are fitted separately for treatment and control group. We get posterior estimated sample means for the response Y by feeding x and s values of the current trial patients to the BART models to calculate $\delta^{(l)}(\mathbf{x}^*)$ and ultimately CATE, see equation 1.

Performance measures

CATE Let $\delta_{ir}^{(k)} = \hat{y}_{ir1}^{(k)} - \hat{y}_{ir0}^{(k)}$, where $\hat{y}_{ir1}^{(k)}$ and $\hat{y}_{ir0}^{(k)}$ are the estimates of treatment and control outcome, respectively for the i^{th} subject, r^{th} replicate and k^{th} posterior realization. The CATE for replicate r can be defined as $\Delta_r = \frac{1}{N_{trial}K} \sum_{i:S_i=0} \sum_{k=1}^K \delta_{ir}^{(k)}$. The estimated CATE is $\hat{\Delta}_C = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R \Delta_r$.

Bias The bias is calculated as the difference between the estimated CATE and the true CATE.

$$Bias = \hat{\Delta}_C - \Delta_C^{true}.$$

Δ_C^{true} in all three scenarios is 0.5.

Credible intervals and CI lengths To find the credible intervals, we compute CATE $\hat{\Delta}_C$ for all the R replicates of generated data. The 2.5 and 97.5 percentiles of these R CATE provide an estimate of a 95% credible interval. The length of a credible interval is the difference between its upper and lower bounds, reflecting the precision and certainty of the parameter estimation. A shorter credible interval indicates higher precision, suggesting that the parameter is known with greater certainty. Conversely, a longer credible interval suggests more uncertainty about the parameter’s true value.

RMSE The root mean square error being the square root the average of the squared difference between estimated and true CATE, provides an indication of the model accuracy. A lower RMSE value suggests that the model’s predictions are close to the actual values, indicating better predictive performance.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R (\Delta_r - \Delta_C^{true})^2}.$$

The results for the simulation study are shown in table 1.

5 Application

Breast cancer study

In this breast cancer study example, we reference the current trial from [Shulman et al. \(2014\)](#), which evaluated the effectiveness of four cycles of cyclophosphamide and doxorubicin (CA) versus four cycles of paclitaxel as adjuvant therapy in women with 0–3 positive axillary lymph nodes. For the external study, we utilize data from [Shulman et al. \(2012\)](#), which investigated whether six cycles of the same chemotherapy regimen were superior to four cycles, with identical treatment arms. Although the studies referenced in this illustration originally included four treatment arms — comprising four and six cycles of both CA and paclitaxel — for the purpose of our analysis, we have simplified the comparison by consolidating these into two arms: CA and paclitaxel, where CA is designated to be the control arm. The covariates included in this analysis are comprised of: ethnicity, group, race, age category, menopause status, receptor status, tumor size, tumor laterality, receptor status ER, receptor status PgR, prior hormonal therapy, histologic grade, type of biopsy, most extensive primary surgery, sentinel node biopsy results, axillary dissection performed, number of positive axillary nodes, length of treatment. For illustrative purposes, subjects with missing covariate values were excluded from the analysis. We also exclude censored subjects and assume that the logarithm of overall survival, the chosen outcome measure, follows a normal distribution ([Buyse et al., 2000](#)). The resulting current data includes 158 subjects, out of which 75 are in the control group and 83, in the treatment group. We borrow 53 control subjects from the external trial. The results for this study, presented in Table 2, show comparable performance across all four methods, with the estimated CATEs for BART, psBART, ps-wBART, and psonlyBART being 0.286, 0.283, 0.270, and 0.291, respectively. The 95% credible intervals are narrowest for psonlyBART and, ps-wBART also exhibit narrower credible intervals than BART and psBART.

6 Discussion

In the first scenario of the simulation study of different BART models, the standard BART model seems to perform better than the others. While psBART achieved a modest reduction in both bias

Methods	Est. CATE	95% CI
BART	0.286	-0.365, 1.103
psBART	0.283	-0.462, 1.070
ps-wBART	0.270	-0.435, 1.003
psonlyBART	0.291	-0.181, 0.883

Table 2: Results for the breast cancer study data.

and credible interval length, it came at the cost of a slight increase in RMSE, highlighting a trade-off between precision and accuracy. ps-wBART showed a slight increase in both bias and RMSE, while maintaining the same credible interval length as the standard BART model. Given that these findings correspond to the fully homogeneous scenario—where the covariate distributions of the current and external trials align perfectly—integrating propensity scores into the BART model may introduce unnecessary complexity, offering little added value. In the second, more heterogeneous scenario, while there is a slight increase in bias for psBART and ps-wBART, the credible interval length shows a modest reduction, and the RMSE remains consistent with that of the standard BART model, indicating stable performance despite the increased heterogeneity. In the most heterogeneous scenario three, ps-wBART exhibits a notable reduction in credible interval length compared to standard BART, despite a slight increase in bias and unchanged RMSE. A similar trend is observed for psBART, highlighting its capacity to tighten interval estimates even in the presence of greater variability. However, psonlyBART consistently underperforms across all scenarios. This underperformance may be attributed to the simplicity of our simulation, where there is only one covariate. In such cases, directly using the single covariate may provide more informative input than relying solely on its propensity score. The loss of information inherent in collapsing a univariate covariate into a propensity score diminishes the model’s ability to capture meaningful patterns, leading to reduced effectiveness.

In scenarios with greater heterogeneity between the current and external datasets, both psBART and ps-wBART demonstrate comparable, if not superior, performance relative to standard BART. Notably, ps-wBART, by using propensity scores as weights, dynamically adjusts the contribution of each observation, making it particularly effective in heterogeneous settings. Similarly, psBART, which includes propensity scores as covariates, helps capture subtle covariate-treatment interactions that might be overlooked by standard BART. The ability of these models to maintain RMSE while improving precision suggests that they offer a practical advantage in complex scenarios where variability between datasets poses challenges for traditional methods.

The breast cancer study reveals that the estimated CATEs after borrowing are comparable across all methods. Interestingly, even psonlyBART produces CATE estimates on par with the other approaches, which contrasts with its underperformance in our simulation results. However, this discrepancy is understandable given the simplicity of our simulation setup. Notably, psonlyBART also yields the narrowest credible intervals, suggesting that in more complex, real-world datasets, the method may perform better than anticipated despite its limitations in simplified scenarios.

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